

DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPECIAL COMPETENCE THROUGH AUTOMATED SYSTEMS OF CONSTRUCTION AND MODELING OF SEWING ITEMS

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Annotation: In the modern education system, the professional qualifications and personal competence of teachers are of great importance. In particular, the development of creative competence of technology teachers is necessary for their success in their professional activities. Creative competence allows teachers to use innovative methods, effectively organize the educational process, and develop students' creative thinking skills. This article analyzes the pedagogical and psychological possibilities of methods for developing creative competence in preparing future technology teachers for professional activities.

Keywords: Creative competence, Technology teacher, Innovative pedagogy, Active learning methods, Design thinking, Project-based learning.

Today, changes are being made in the education system on a global scale. In particular, the issues of integrating innovative technologies into the educational process and developing the creative competence of modern teachers are of urgent importance. Teaching technology requires not only the transfer of theoretical knowledge, but also the development of students' creative abilities, the formation of innovative approaches in them necessary for solving modern problems. In this regard, the development of creative competence is one of the most important tasks in preparing future technology teachers for professional activity. Creative competence is a person's ability to approach problems creatively, to create innovations and to develop effective methods. In the context of modern technologies and their application in education, teachers are required not only to be knowledgeable, but also to be able to creatively apply their knowledge and experience. In this regard, pedagogical and psychological approaches and innovative methods play a great role. The development of creative competence in the educational process, along with increasing students' creative thinking skills, helps them develop unique and effective approaches to solving problem situations. This not only increases the professional skills of technology teachers, but also forms their effective pedagogical relationships with students. This article is aimed at analyzing the pedagogical and psychological potential of methods designed to develop creative

competence in future technology teachers. The advantages of using modern pedagogical technologies, creative approaches and creative methods in the educational process and their role in the activities of teachers are widely covered. In turn, the issue of forming and developing creative competence in education is approached based on national and international experience, and recommendations are given that serve to ensure the professional and personal development of future teachers. At the same time, the psychological foundations of the methods and approaches used in the development of creative competence are also deeply analyzed. Scientific research on the issue of developing creative competence of future technology teachers was carried out on the basis of various pedagogical and psychological approaches.

The vocational education system today plays a key role in training high-quality specialists. The need to improve the effectiveness of educational methodologies in clothing design and modeling, and to introduce modern pedagogical technologies for students is increasing day by day. Innovative approaches, information technologies and interactive pedagogical methods play an important role in the modern educational process in clothing design and modeling. The purpose of the article is to develop new approaches to integrating innovative approaches in improving the methodology of teaching students how to design and model clothes.

There are several important studies in the field of educational methodology for clothing design and modeling. In particular, the research conducted by Gulnora Jumayeva emphasizes the importance of interactive communication between the teacher and the student in teaching students the basics of clothing design. "The role and significance of innovative technologies in the development of education" in turn explores the possibilities of using innovative techniques in developing practical skills in students using modern pedagogical technologies. The study "The essence and theoretical foundations of innovative educational technologies" examines in detail the methods of using modern information technologies in modeling. In addition, there is new literature on the methodological aspects of design and modeling in clothing design. The work "Innovative information technologies in the educational process" emphasizes the importance of developing students' creative thinking in the design process, which helps to form in-depth knowledge of clothing design [1, 2]. Q. M. Abdullaeva, the content of the knowledge, skills and qualifications that future teachers of vocational education should possess in special disciplines was scientifically studied, a methodology for designing and modeling sewing products in conjunction with design elements was developed [3]. In the scientific research work of N. N. Karimova, the content of the professional competence of future teachers of vocational education and the problems of its development were studied, and the structural structure of the professional

competence of future teachers of vocational education in the direction of design (costume) education, a methodology for developing students' creative abilities based on integrative training in general vocational and specialized disciplines (fashion illustration, casual) was developed [4]. S. Yu. Rajabova's scientific research study studied the methodology for developing the design and technological competence of future vocational teachers, and improved the methodology for organizing practical training in general and specialized subjects through the use of the effective possibilities of interactive teaching methods such as effective practical result, team creative collections and buddying. At the same time, the stages of performing tasks of an innovative nature: creative project, for-sketch, combinatorics, deconstruction, pattern gradation, sketch stylization and transformation are aimed at maximally satisfying professional needs and employer requirements. These methodologies were developed using computer programs such as "Autodesk Sketchbook", "NanoCAD", "Marvelous Designer". The following methods are used as the main methodology of the study: 1. Analytical method - identification of innovative pedagogical approaches to the design and modeling of clothing through the analysis of existing scientific literature and practical experience. 2. Experimental method - the introduction of innovative technologies into educational processes as an experiment, measurement and evaluation of results. 3. Quantification - statistical analysis of materials studied by students and learning outcomes. 4. Sociological research methods - conducting questionnaires and interviews to exchange ideas between students and teachers, analyze experiences and views.

The results of the study show that the use of innovative technologies in the design and modeling of clothing increases students' motivation to study and develops practical skills. For example, the use of virtual modeling programs allows students to quickly create clothing designs and see their changes in real time. In addition, interactive teaching methods, such as simulations and online courses, serve as an effective tool for students to consolidate their knowledge and master new methods [7, 9]. Research also shows that developing creative thinking in students during the process of teaching fashion design is an important factor in preparing them for professional activities. The integration of innovative technologies helps to improve not only students' academic skills, but also their creative potential.

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